

COMPREHENSIVE WEB TECHNOLOGIES AIMED AT INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF COOPERATION WITH HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS AND PERSONNEL CUSTOMERS

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Annotation: This article presents integrated web technologies aimed at increasing the efficiency of cooperation with higher educational institutions and customer employees, the current state of public online open courses developed by universities in developed foreign countries, various aspects and opportunities that integrated web technologies provide teachers. The role of integrated web technologies in preparing future engineers for professional activities is also highlighted.

Key words: higher education institution, education, science, web technologies, network, society, technology, educational material, pedagogy, psychology, manufacturing industries.

The development of the electronic education system further expands the practice of its effective use in the educational process and requires a careful look at current trends and existing world experience that determine the main vectors of development of the current educational paradigm. Today, millions of people around the world are undergoing distance education in almost all fields: law, engineering, programming, language learning, etc. Online education is becoming increasingly widespread due to its freeness, versatility and convenience. Among them, one of the most promising trends in the development of e-education in recent years has been the formation of state open online courses, which are based on the idea of public education with equal opportunities for all. Anyone from all over the world has the opportunity to study this course for free. Provides academic courses that allow teachers and hundreds of thousands of students (course participants) to organize free communication.

Today, the number of people who have taken advantage of the capabilities of LLC is several million. Other leading universities and educational centers around the world are also emphasizing online education. It is also possible to read expensive textbooks for free in an online environment. Currently, it is possible to work in certain groups on the Internet. This is also important in education. Ability to save group work data online. They can also be used by next year's students. In traditional education this opportunity is limited.

Public Open Online Courses (OPOCs) are offered by many universities around the world to anyone in any part of the world using distance learning technologies to deliver academic courses to professors and hundreds of thousands of students (course takers). Today, the number of people who have taken advantage of the capabilities of LLC is several million. Other leading universities and educational centers around the world are also emphasizing online education. It is also possible to read expensive textbooks for free in an online environment. Currently, it is possible to work in certain groups on the Internet.

This is also important in education. Ability to save group work data online. They can also be used by next year's students. In traditional education this opportunity is limited.

Another advantage of public open online courses is that the duration of training is determined by the student himself, that is, the student begins studying at the time of his choice and studies the materials under the supervision of the teacher. Mastery is determined by completing assignments and tests. The faster a student masters this program, the faster he will complete his studies and receive a certificate. If he is unable to master the program, he will be given the opportunity to work independently and continue his studies.

The main features of OOK are associated with such tasks as the implementation of the principles of continuity and individual orientation of education, bringing modern scientific ideas into an understandable form:

- 1) mass participation, that is, the number of course participants is not limited;
- 2) openness, i.e. providing free knowledge to everyone, in a place and time convenient for them;
- 3) the integrity of the courses, that is, the courses include not only fragments of educational material, but also practical exercises, communication and materials that control the acquired knowledge;
- 4) the opportunity to receive a certificate upon successful completion of the course.

Teaching in public open online courses is a teaching system in which the teacher and student are at a certain distance. This requires the teacher to organize a lesson based on such means as computers, satellite communications, cable television.

Public open online education:

- consists of a modern form of open education;

- focused on the use of computer education;
- modern communication technologies are used for active communication with teachers and other students.

The online education system provides many opportunities for higher education institutions, corporations and government organizations. After classes, you can give additional tasks and implement exchange programs at the global level. Although the number of students per class is limited, online learning offers the opportunity to teach many people at the same time. Online education allows shy students to learn more actively. It can be difficult to remember all the information learned in traditional classes. And in online education it will be possible to repeat knowledge and share it on a global scale.

In the course of our research, web technologies were created to ensure employment of graduates of the Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute and present them to employers. When creating web technologies, an interactive system for managing the practice of professors and teachers of an educational institution, candidates for senior researchers, undergraduates and graduate students was developed, the software of which was based on the Wordpress content management system. Wordpress CMS runs in network sites mode, which means that it is designed for a large number of users. In addition, this system has created plugins (utility program) to facilitate the operation of the system. These include those that determine the number of students, upload photographs of the system owner, and create new users for faculties and departments based on a single template. The fact that Wordpress is open source software allows you to make necessary additions and changes to it. Users also have the ability to easily change their appearance based on the content of web technologies.

As an important means of popularizing and promoting best practices, the creation of professional activity systems announced via the Internet and regular updating of information about university employees and students, both in time and in nature, is the most convenient form of systematic description. .

The personality of the teacher occupies a central place in every educational institution. He should properly plan educational, scientific and cultural events when organizing his activities, quickly adapt to the requirements of the changing times in order to constantly improve his professional and pedagogical skills.

Modern educational institutions require a new class of teachers-creative thinkers who can use modern teaching methods and technologies, methods of pedagogical and psychological diagnostics, methods of independent design of the pedagogical process based on specific practical activities.

It is known that the competitiveness of specialists in the labor market largely depends on their ability to master advanced technologies and adapt to changing working conditions.

It is extremely important to determine the types of Internet services and their nature in order to determine the possibilities of using integrated web technologies in the educational process and its effectiveness. It is these identified data that help differentiate organizational forms and practices on the Internet.

All educational web technologies on the Internet can be divided into several types.

Internet sources of consultations are various teleconferences, virtual pedagogical councils, virtual methodological, associative problem councils, virtual cafes, etc.

Examples of online learning resources include distance learning, virtual schools, laboratories, and web-based classes.

Examples of Internet information sources can be electronic textbooks, reference books, electronic libraries, dictionaries, catalogs, and virtual museums.

Detailed information about the educational areas of educational institutions is covered in the presented Internet resources.

Assessment sources on the Internet include teletesting, distance competitions, various quizzes and competitions.

In the search for ways to improve the quality of education, the problem arises of creating a coordinated model of blended education that combines the best of modern education with the systematic and effective use of modern integrated web technologies. Many years of international and domestic experience show that the introduction of integrated web technologies into the traditional educational process, as a rule, requires a radical change in the methodology of organizing the educational process and the introduction of new forms of various directions.

As a result, traditional forms of implementation of the educational process can be presented in a modified form, most adapted to integrated web technologies.

Currently, a lot of experience has been accumulated in the implementation of integrated web technologies, and in pedagogical practice there are three of its models, differing in the ratio of time and load distribution between classes, electronic components, and teaching strategy:

- classes conducted using web technologies - a model dedicated to independent work of students in an electronic environment up to 30% of the educational time, online consultations, ongoing and intermediate control, etc.

- blended learning - a model built on the integration and complementarity of traditional and web technologies (up to 80% of the time), which involves replacing part of traditional educational activities with various types of educational interaction in the electronic environment.

- distance education (online learning) – a model in which 90-100% of the educational process is carried out in an electronic environment.

At the same time, the use of distance education often worsens the quality of student learning, which researchers explain by a number of disadvantages: the lack of social contact with other participants in the study, the risk of students misinterpreting theoretical material, and the need for a high level of self-training for students.

With the help of websites created for educational institutions, teachers create the opportunity for students to study remotely. Websites created for educational institutions are especially convenient for students who find it difficult to attend educational institutions. In addition, students will acquire the culture, skills and competencies of working with information technology. Using websites created for educational institutions during the lesson opens up great opportunities.

The use of educational web technologies in the educational process provides teachers with a number of opportunities:

Another advantage of web technologies aimed at education is that the student himself determines the duration of training, that is, the student begins studying at the time of his choice and studies the materials under the supervision of the teacher. A student's mastery is determined by completing assignments and tests. The faster the student masters the task, the faster he will graduate. If he is unable to master the program, he will be given the opportunity to work independently and continue his studies. Educational web technology materials mainly consist of:

An important and complex task is the cataloging of websites created for higher educational institutions of our republic, the promotion of electronic educational literature prepared in higher educational institutions of the republic among all higher educational institutions. The leadership of our country pays serious attention to finding a positive solution to this issue and introducing into the educational process electronic educational resources created for higher educational institutions and websites of educational institutions.

Taking into account the above, we have developed an integrated web technology “Interactive Practice Management System”, aimed at interactive

management of student practices, aimed at developing the production and technological competencies of students. As a result of this, it becomes possible to carry out educational, industrial, qualification and pre-diploma practice for students of higher educational institutions while ensuring integration with production enterprises, as well as to constantly monitor students' internships.

This shows the overall status of the system, i.e. you can enter users, add groups, enter teachers, post the necessary documents, control the sending of assignments to students, control the teacher's grading of assignments.

This section provides complete information about system users. That is, information is provided about the full names, surnames, email addresses of users registered in the system, types and groups of users.

In this department, students are given daily assignments during practice, the sending of assigned assignments to students and their completion by students is monitored.

In this section, it is possible to evaluate students' assignments during practice, that is, analyze the assignment, leave a comment, evaluate it and send it to the user.

Thus, the focus on the process-resultative approach, which focuses on the special nature of the connection between the procedural and resultant sides of the desired process in the development of production and technological competence of students, has a direct impact on the development of integrated web technologies

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